

The Influence of Differences between Chinese and Western Diet Culture on International Business

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Abstract: Based on John Bailey's theory of Cultural Adaptation, this research mainly focuses on the differences between Chinese and the United States' diet culture, analyzes the background and causes of differences between Chinese and Western diet cultures, and further expounds the long-standing exchanges and collisions between Chinese and Western diet culture differences so as to reveal the development status and existing problems of international business activities under the diet culture differences. The study is aimed to provide certain references for the elimination of cultural barrier in international business communication and thus promote the smooth development of international market.

Key words: Diet culture; cultural difference; international business

I. Introduction

As a pillar of national survival and development, culture plays a very important role in the life of the country and people. Diet is the root of people's lives, and different ethnic cultures create a unique food culture. With the rapid development of economic globalization, the commerce between countries is becoming more and more frequent, and culture has become an important force to support the long-term development of international business contacts (Bian 2004). There are obvious differences on the attitude and content of the diet culture in different countries, at present, international exchanges are becoming more and more close, and the differences between Chinese and Western diet culture are constantly being exchanged and colliding in international exchanges, which cannot be ignored in the foreign business activities of different countries. It can be seen that it is very important to understand the differences in Chinese and Western diet culture and the impact of international business in this kind of difference.

At home and abroad on the differences in Chinese and Western cultural studies of the research play a catalytic role in the studies of cultural differences between the Chinese and Western. For example, in the book "China to Chinatown Chinese Food in the West"(2002) by the author of the British author John·Anthony·George·Roberts, westerners have made an objective and valuable comment on the viewpoint of Chinese diet culture, helping us to learn more about the concept of westerners' treatment of Chinese diet culture. But this book is limited to the study of differences in Chinese and Western diet culture, and did not further analyze the influence of Chinese and Western diet culture differences on international business. The existing academic researches, for the most part, confined to the differences between Chinese and Western diet culture research, and did not further explore the role and influence of diet culture differences in intercultural communication and international business. At present, at home and abroad, there is a lack of special research on the influence of Chinese and Western diet culture on international business. It remains to be further studied and discussed.

This research breaks through the limitations of academic researches and probes into the influence of Chinese and Western diet culture on international business. In the case of diet culture difference between China and the United States, and based on the theory of "Cultural Adaptation", while the literature review of previous studies, the article is divided into three parts to study the influence of Chinese and Western diet culture differences on international business. The first part introduces the background and reasons for the differences between Chinese and Western diet cultures, as well as the exchange and collision of dietary culture differences. The second part bases on cases of Chinese and Western diet culture differences in international business performance and the impact of the analysis, and further clarifies the understanding of Chinese and Western diet culture differences on

international business the importance of long-term development; In the third part, based on the previous analysis, this research puts forward the inspiration for the development of international business activities in the future.

Understanding the influence of differences between Chinese and Western diet culture on international business enables our enterprises to participate in the process of international economic competition, to adapt to the economic and cultural environment between each other, to obtain competitive advantage and access to international business activities initiative. It is worthy to say that Chinese enterprise must pay attention to the problem in international business, which is also the purpose of this research and the original intention.

II. Introduction to Chinese and Western diet culture

In each country culture, diet culture is a vital existence, diet culture differences between the exchange and collision of the establishment and development of the international business plays a considerable role (Fahey 1984). If China wants to be engaged in international business successfully, we must fully understand the international diet culture differences. Whether in China or any country in the world, in order to occupy an important position under the great trend of economic globalization, it is necessary to understand the differences in diet culture among international cooperatives with the same prerequisite.

The diet culture has been formed over a long period of time, and it has a close relationship with the development of mankind and society. Food is an essential part of human being's life, and it is not only important to improve the quality of mankind's life, but also can promote the development of society. The differences between Chinese and Western diet cultures are already well worth exploring in China and the United States. Chinese dietary culture is extensive and profound. There is an old saying in China called "people eat for the day". Comparing the food to the sky, the Chinese people's attention to the diet can be seen. And the Western diet is delicate and specialize the system. Although the historical origins of the United States cannot be compared with China, it has also formed a diet culture with its own characteristics through the injection and integration of various cultures.

Value is the principles, quality, or standards which guides human behavior. Different nations or countries are certainly having discrepancies in their values. Chinese and Westerner have different basic concepts of values. About the differences between Chinese and Western diet cultures, there are significant differences in historical background and values, as well as eating habits and diet, and each has its own advantages (Chen 2007). The collision and communication between Chinese and Western diet culture can facilitate the development of human civilization. Over the years, the oriental diet culture and Western diet culture has been a hot topic in academic field. The differences between Chinese and Western diet culture is also one of the manifestations about cross-culture communication phenomenon. For the study of diet culture, it requires the mutual understanding and tolerance between different cultures. Under the background of globalization of economic and cultural integration, we can study and fully understand the differences of Chinese and Western diet culture, to enhance the mutual understanding between people from different countries, enjoying the food at the same time, promote the spread, exchange and fusion of national culture.

In summary, the differences between Chinese and Western cultures have long been poorly different, the difference between Chinese and Western cultures has created a difference between Chinese and Western diet culture, and this difference comes from the different cultural backgrounds and historical reasons. The first part of this research will explore the two countries in China and the United States as an example of the difference between Chinese and Western diet cultures' story. China's diet culture has a long history. According to records, since the ape-man era of cooking with cooked food, China has 170-180 million years of cooked food history. From the "cooking" of the fire in the water, China has a history of at least 10,000 years, which is unique among the nations of the world (Wang, 2006). Chinese have always maintained a good tradition of using materials and materials. Apart from cooking delicious dishes, the Chinese diet culture also draw attention to diet therapy and health care. Moreover, China's cooking for food has a rich and varied production techniques, including steamed, fried, which is unique to the Chinese nation. China has vast land and rich resources, the region's flavor genres have their own characteristics, and these characteristics jointly create a splendid and colorful Chinese diet culture. It can be seen that China's cultural inside story is quite deep.

In the United States, the situation is more special. The United States has a vast land, short history and more than 100 countries of different races immigrants to the United States, making United States the world's largest

melting pot. Therefore, the formation of American food dishes also comes from this “melting pot”. Due to the impact of early immigrants, the traditional American cuisine is like the traditional Americans, its characteristics are “rough mad real” (Xu 2001). They eat fresh raw materials, do not rely on additives and flavoring, and make food to keep the original flavor. The cooking process is simple and quick, whether it is grilled or fried, there is no complicated process, and there are not too many fancy decorations. The food on the plate can be happy to eat a full meal.

China and the United States have different origins in dietary culture, and the historical background is also different. The formation of the diet culture in China and the United States is not only affected by the geographical factors such as terrain and topography, sea-land location, and climatic factors, but also the influence of human factors such as political, economic, national culture and religion. Thus, there is a great difference in nature. If China is a farming culture-based land culture, the West is a kind of livestock culture as the representative of the marine culture. There are many reasons for the differences in Chinese and Western diet culture, such as differences in diet and eating habits, and then let us further explore the differences between Chinese and Western diet culture from these causes.

On the one hand, there are differences in the concept of diet. Chinese people pay attention to the organic unity of food color, aroma and taste. Chinese people are very strict with the requirements of food. The food should have a beautiful appearance, causing people’s appetite, food but also have their own unique incense. The most important thing is that the taste is the Chinese people’s pursuit of the highest state of the diet. In addition, the Chinese cuisine is not only very delicious and tasty, but also very pleasing to your senses and many of dishes have very allegoric and fancy name. To sum up, the Chinese people in the pursuit of food attitude is very serious. The Chinese have the diet culture of our own which are quite different from the Western. In the West, people draw more attention to the nutrition of diet rather than the looks or fancy name of it. Western people put more emphasis on the scientific and reasonable collocation of dietary nutrition. Compared to the “perfect combination of color aroma taste and appearance”, they attach more importance to the food contains calories, vitamins and protein and other nutrients, as well as the daily intake of these nutrients, so westerners may be likely to eat the same or more rich nutritional value of food.

In addition, due to the difference of Chinese and Western ideas and value orientation, the manifestation of dietary concept is that the Chinese dietary concept emphasizes emotional and artistic, and we pursuit the eating tastes, while the Western concept of eating is a rational, emphasizing the concept of scientific and healthy.

On the other hand, there are differences in the eating habits. From the point of view of food, the Chinese people like to eat coarse grains, while westerner’s prefer refined grains such as refined white flour. Chinese people love soy milk, tofu, fermented bean curd and other soy products, while the West is keen on milk, cheese and other dairy products. What is also worth noticing a very obvious difference is that Chinese people like to eat cooked food, are keen on hyped and that food should be cooked to eat, and the westerners, they like raw vegetables, such as salad, as well as half cooked or even three mature still dropping the blood of the steak.

In China, everything is edible. It seems that we dare to eat everything and everything can be eatable in Chinese food, whether it is from the sea, or from the land, or from the sky, or whether it is domestic or wild. Foreigners cannot imagine that we eat some foods, such as snakes, dogs and even frogs. When we sell the meat from poultry and animals, we usually sell it as a whole, or cut the meat from the whole body.

As is known to all, the Chinese have been eating with chopsticks and spoons, and use a plate with a bowl to eat food since ancient times. Among them, chopsticks are one of the symbols of Chinese diet culture (Zhao 2008). While westerners use knives and forks to eat, with the plate to install food, and even different styles of spoons have their own usage Chopsticks and knives and forks are the most representative of the Chinese and Western dietary tableware, affecting the different eating habits and lifestyles in China and the West. Therefore, for all reasons, there are obvious differences between Chinese and Western diet culture.

Nowadays, the development of the situation makes exchange and collision of the cultural differences between countries become inevitable. In order to cater to the trend of the world of the new situation, the exchange and collision of Chinese and Western diet culture differences has become an inevitable trend.

The Chinese table is very lively, which means everyone is sitting around together, eating the same dish, while in the west, everyone has their own plate, and the food is eaten in their own tray (He 2009). Because of the different culture, in the table etiquette, the Chinese and Western diet culture inevitably come into collision. In the

Chinese table culture, it is often found that other people frequently get food and urge somebody to drink and so on. In the Western feast, the host usually only give guests a dish, the rest of the guests by the edible. In the Chinese family dinner, we normally cook more food than guests eat. If you finish your food at meal, the host and hostess normally add more and more food in your bowl to show that they are polite to the guests. And they will always say: "Eat more". However, the Americans never force you to eat more. If you stop eating, they will think you are full. This is the difference between Chinese and Western diet culture. Let's assume that it would be an awkward and hilarious banquet if the Chinese and Westerners who were not aware of the differences in Chinese and Western diet culture were sitting on the same table for dinner. Ignorance of the difference between Chinese and Western diet culture can lead to negative impressions from the other side.

III. Diet cultural differences and influences of different diet cultures on international business

Along with the rapid development of science and technology, China has become one of the world's largest import and export countries, and the world is becoming a global village. As we all know, different countries have different cultures, and cultures play a very important part in the enterprise, especially in the foreign trade.

3.1 Diet cultural differences in international business

The most obvious difference between foreign trade and domestic trade is that foreign trade needs to deal with people of different cultures. In recent years, with the increasing frequency of international business and the increase of foreign business activities, in the process of international business, the differences in diet culture between China and the West have been highlighted. The differences in diet culture have led to cultural collisions and even conflicts in international business dealings. And the differences between Chinese and Western diets have directly affected the smooth progress of international business dealings.

In China's business activities, there is a unique culture called the dining culture. Chinese people are more implicative, do not like to show their attitude straightforward, and always negotiate other business deal at the dinner table. Chinese businessmen tend to negotiate business in a rather indirect way, rather than being as direct as American businessmen (Hayford 1978). They avoid the theme of business negotiations and focus on the wine of the table and show the sincerity of business cooperation with the amount of alcohol. Food and beverage will become a tool to ease the atmosphere, in order to prevent the negotiations stalemate, smart dinner leaders will stand out from time to time to put forward a cup, ease the mood and then continue to discuss, which is also negotiating matters to choose in one of the important reasons for the meal, and many of China's economic business talks about in the dinner on the finalized. In China's business activities, there are many mysteries of wine on the table.

In contrast, in the United States business activities, the Americans seem more casual, American business travel breakfast and lunch dating business. Hospitality business guests are mostly roasted steak, roast chicken and other dishes, coupled with some vegetable salad and dessert after dessert is a table meal. Americans are doing things neatly and do not like to beat around the bush. At the negotiating table, they will quickly start a substantive conversation. It is also because Americans have such a simple attitude that negotiating with the Americans must be clear to tell them the answer, not vague. At this point, there is a significant difference in terms of Chinese "always saving face" and "very little direct rejection of each other recommendations".

International business activities are not only an economic activity, but also a cultural activity, one of the features is the cultural differences that are highlighted in international business activities. Americans greatly at odds with China's diet culture and dining etiquette. Americans in China participate in business activities such as dinner, and they will inevitably feel uncomfortable, and even cause some misunderstanding between the two countries (Zhao 2002).

In December 2014, the Guangming Online reported oral news of several Americans attending the China business dinner. The presence of several Americans said it is difficult to understand the business dinner, they say that there is a big difference between Chinese and Westerners' way of eating. Chinese dinner has four points: one to pomp, two to face, three to wine and meat, four to death. Chinese people cannot eat without meat. All kinds of animals are made on the table dishes, from the head to the claws, no part of the animal is not eaten by the Chinese. In addition, the Chinese banquet is rich in leftovers, and after the meal is over, no one will pack up the leftovers. It seems that the package leftovers are very disgraceful things. Americans, however, are pursuing a disc-saving

behavior of food. Another thing is that the Chinese business dinner is inseparable from drinking, not only drinking, but also forcing others to drink.

The Americans in the report were surprised and unreceptive to the Chinese business dinner. They think that China's business dinner is extravagant waste and try to persuade others to drink regardless of the feelings of others. Therefore, according to the case, it can be found that the negative effects of diet cultural differences will be a major obstacle to the development of trade cooperation.

The differences of wine cultures between Chinese and Western is also worth mentioning. In terms of drinking etiquette, Chinese drinking etiquette shows respect for drinkers. Who is the host, who is the guest, it always has a fixed seat, and there is a fixed order of toast. When toasting, you should start with your master, the host does not finish the wine, the other person is not qualified to toast, if disorderly order is to be punished. While westerners drink wine etiquette, it reflects the respect for wine.

In China, wine is often used as a tool. Wine in the eyes of Chinese people is more as a communication tool, so in the Chinese wine culture, there is a lack of scientific and systematic theoretical analysis and evaluation of the wine itself, and more concerned with the wonderful effect of drinking. In the West, the purpose of drinking is often very simple, in order to enjoy the wine and drink.

This case reflects the problems that existed in China's business dinner, and even today, these problems still exist. Americans will have such a cultural impression of China's business dinner, and the reasons for this study directly reveal that there is a great difference between Chinese and Western diet culture in international business activities.

At the same time, from the above real case is not difficult to see that the differences between Chinese and Western diet cultures have a great impact on the Sino-US business dealings. It is very important to have an in-depth understanding of the differences between Chinese and Western diet cultures and the impact of these differences on the international business activities.

3.2 Influences of different diet cultures on international business

If there is a collision, there will be communication. The exchange of Chinese and Western cultures has a long history, and the exchange of Chinese and Western diet culture have been reflected in our daily life. With the increasing number of Chinese and Western exchanges, more and more Chinese people are beginning to recognize and promote the western diet. Western restaurant has been seen in China. Western-style food is also increasingly integrated into the daily life of the Chinese people, more and more Chinese people like eating bread and drinking milk as their own breakfast, but also learns the diet concept of Westerners to pursue a healthy and nutritious (Yang 2010). Similarly, the Chinese diet culture has spread and influenced the Western eating habits. More and more Chinese restaurants have sprung up in foreign countries, and delicious Chinese food has succeeded in capturing the countless foreigners' stomachs. The United States used to count the number of foreign restaurants in the United States, and the results showed that in the number of foreign restaurants in the United States, Chinese restaurants topped the list. While spreading Chinese food, in order to cater to the taste of local foreigners, Chinese restaurants incorporate the local production process and incorporate them into Chinese dishes.

Cultural difference is an objective existence, which has long been formed in history. To succeed in different cultural exchanges, it is necessary to enhance intercultural consciousness, so as to establish the concept of cultural differences, understand and respect different cultural characteristics, understand each other behavior characteristic and the value idea, and set up mutual trust and mutual benefit and win-win belief. The study on the differences in diet culture requires the mutual understanding and appreciation between different cultures, so that all the people who come from different countries that can enhance mutual understanding with each other, enjoy the different feelings of different diet culture, and enhance the exchange and integration of cultural differences. This is the communication between Chinese and Western diet cultures. Today, the exchange and collision of Chinese and Western diet culture is not rare, and as time goes on, more exchanges and collisions will emerge.

The impact of diet culture on business is extensive and profound. In the process of international business in China and the United States, the differences of China and the West diet culture both communicate with each other, and hard to avoid some collisions, but eventually to development of national economy and adapt to the globalization process and constantly understanding and tolerance of differences between China and the West diet culture. As John Bailey's theory of "Cultural Adaptation", to deal with the trend of economic globalization, and

promote the development of international business, we must strive to balance their traditional culture and identity with the rest of the world's multicultural integration. In the process of cultural adaptation, in fact, there are actually to the mutual contact of two different cultures will have an impact.

With the pace of globalization in the world, in the background of economic, cultural, information exchange and collision, the Chinese and Western diet culture will be in the collision of communication, in the exchange of complementary. With the rapidly development of China's economic strength, China's international status has improved. The foreigners in expanding numbers have come to China. In this process, there has exert a favorable and positive impact on the diet culture inevitably has merged. This will enhance the mutual understanding between the Chinese and Western sides, and in harmony with the other diet culture differences at the same time, we can promote world peace and development, and promote international business cooperation and development opportunities around the world. The positive influences of Sino-American diet cultural differences on international business are bellowed the following points:

In order to carry out international business with the United States and other Western countries, the Chinese people in the business negotiations with the Westerners to change the local negotiating style, there will not be an obnoxious wine table culture and flattering gift-giving culture, but it is gradually adapting to western business eating habits and changing to a serious and polite business meal (Liu 2009). This will not only allow foreign economic partners to feel the sincerity of China, but also to avoid foreigners to leave some of the negative impression of Chinese diet culture. Similarly, the United States and other Western countries in the pursuit of business relations with China, and also gradually adapt to and accept the Chinese diet culture.

A growing number of foreign companies are willing to take business talks with Chinese enterprises in Chinese restaurants in Chinatown or in China. At present, in the United States and other Western countries, there are numerous Chinese restaurants, which have driven economic benefits to a certain extent. Likewise, in China, Western fast food restaurants such as Kentucky Fried Chicken, McDonald's, Burger King and other Western fast food restaurants everywhere. The emergence of Chinese and Western restaurants has led to a significant increase in economic growth. Due to the understanding of diet culture differences between Chinese and Western countries, it avoids a lot of unnecessary embarrassing scenes and trouble problems. The two sides have jointly created a comfortable and peaceful environment so that both sides can speak freely and reach consensus.

3.3 Implications and enlightenments on future international business

Larry (2009) pointed out that groups with different cultural background in the multicultural society of cultural adaptation problems should be focused on, because of different cultural backgrounds between groups is how to peaceful development and harmonious multicultural countries cannot be ignored. International business is a cross-border economic activity, and the two countries reach a consensus process based on common business interests. Differences between Chinese and Western diet culture are an important factor affecting international business. International business activities are an important means to promote the exchange and integration of Chinese and Western diet culture. At the same time, in-depth understanding of differences in Chinese and Western diet culture can promote the smooth progress of international business activities. Before the international business, it is helpful to avoid the misunderstandings and contradictions caused by differences in diet culture among international business partners, so we have to fully understanding of Chinese and Western diet culture differences and to carry out the research, try to minimize and avoid the negative effects of cultural differences. To this, we can realize that this is a meaningful thing.

In addition, the traditional culture of far-reaching, business activities in the diet culture is full of advantages and disadvantages. These so many aspects of the factors affect even determine the success or failure of international business in China. Therefore, in the process of international business, more attention should be paid to the understanding of the differences between Chinese and Western diet culture. Take the essence and discard the dregs. To understand the significance of Chinese and Western diet culture differences in international business dealings is also reflected in the following three points:

First of all, on the basis of seeking common ground while reserving differences, we can promote the common progress and development of Chinese and Western diet culture, and promote the process of economic globalization and world integration. Second, both can cross cultural communication barriers, and it can cultivate international business personnel in cross-cultural communication is the ability to adapt. The last but not least, the

understanding of Chinese and Western diet culture differences on absorbing the essence of the western diet culture, and carry forward the Chinese diet culture, especially the development and operation of food and beverage products in China's tourist hotels have very important guiding significance.

Everything we know is related to culture. It is very powerful, to a certain extent; culture is a kind of invisible strength. If we can properly handle cultural conflicts well, it can help strengthen the vitality and competitiveness of enterprises, and thus constitute the motive of enterprises' development. The existence of the cultural conflict makes businessmen realize the diet cultural difference between different values and different nationalities, and in this way it expands the businessman's vision. While dealing with some problems, it may broaden their thoughts, and urge them to realize the important significance of scientific and proper handling of diet cultural conflict for the survival and development of the enterprises.

To sum up, it is of great significance and profound significance to understand the differences between Chinese and Western diet culture and to improve the efficiency of international business and promote the effective implementation of intercultural communication.

For many years, we all know the importance to learn the culture form different countries. Thanks to the development of communication technology, the progress of transportation technology, the economic globalization and the augmentation of population, the world is experiencing profound changes in multi-polarization and globalization. Accordingly, the study of cultural differences has become more and more important and urgent. People are increasingly aware of the significance and the impact of the study on differences between Chinese and Western diet culture.

One of the theories in the theory of "Cultural Adaptation" is: Integration - the individual in cultural adaptation not only to maintain the traditional culture, but also focus on other groups for daily exchanges. When the mainstream culture adopts multiculturalism strategy, the non-mainstream group will adopt the integration strategy. Under the guidance of theory of "Cultural Adaptation", we can get the following enlightenment:

On the one hand, face up and respect the differences in diet culture. The awareness of cultural differences is a necessary condition for success. If we want to communicate more effectively with people from other cultures, we not only should learn their diet cultures, but also should deeply know our own diet culture. We have to eliminate the prejudice against the cultural differences, in the business of foreign counterparts; we have to learn to use a friendly and open mind to accept the foreign culture, so as to promote the harmonious conduct of international business. Chinese businessmen, in the meantime, should be culturally sensitive and try to learn each other's culture as much as possible. There is no need to try to fully adapt themselves to the other side's culture and do not need to judge each other cultural system. We cannot impose our culture on other people, nor can we measure other people's culture with our own culture. What is more important is that we should not be crazy about foreign things and obsequious to foreigner; do not adhere to the principle. In the process of international business, we must rationally deal with the problems caused by cultural differences.

On the other hand, we need to correctly handle the differences of the diet culture in international business. We must consciously cultivate cross-cultural awareness, understand the cultural background of different countries and cultural differences in diet, and on this basis, foster strengths and circumvent weaknesses. At the same time, we have to establish the correct international cooperation policy and strategy, and to carry out reasonable and comfortable international business contacts, in order to improve the success rate of international business cooperation.

Only by doing this can we establish permanent friendship and long-term cooperation with our international business partners, and be able to achieve success in the long-term development of international business. It is really hoped that these revelations will be of some help to multinational business workers. Hoping to understand the influence of differences between China and the Western diet culture on international business contacts, can promote the further development of international business. Under the theme of peace and development, it is time to bring the world more closely linked together, and to jointly promote the prosperity of the global economy boom.

IV. Conclusion

There is no doubt that we are now in the era of rapid development of information technology. In order to promote the further development of economic globalization and promote exchanges and links between countries, understanding the differences between Chinese and Western diet culture is more and more important in

international business. The differences between Chinese and Western diet culture under the close contact with international dealings have been constantly exchanging and colliding. The international business contacts have become more and more frequent, and the differences in diet culture have played a more and more important role in promoting international business activities.

This research aims to focus on the impact of Sino-US diet cultural differences on international business. Through the analysis of the historical background and causes of the differences between Chinese and Western, it is concluded that the differences between Chinese and Western diet culture have existed for a long time, and they have been constantly communicating and colliding. The study, on the basis of cases, explores the real business in the international business process: if the differences between Chinese and Western diet culture do not fully understand by the international business person, then they will make a lot of misunderstanding and difficult to reconcile the contradictions, and even lead to the international business at an impasse. Further, it reveals that understanding the differences of Chinese and Western diet culture has brought positive influence on the cultural, economic and business environment in international business. Common ground while reserving differences is the long-term development strategy. It is hoped that the study can give scholars of relevant field a little inspiration and provide certain references for intercultural business communication.

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